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THE CONCEPT OF DARK AND DEEP NETS, ACTIVITIES AND POPULAR MARKETS IN THEM

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu keng qamrovli maqola Internetning berkitilgan tarmoqlaridagi noqonuniy faoliyat va mashhur bozorlarni o'rganib, "Dark net" va "Deep net"lar tushunchasini o'rganadi. Dark va Deep Netning farqlovchi xususiyatlari va funksiyalarini chuqur tahlil qilinib, ushbu tarmoqlarda anonimlik, shifrlash va kuzatilmaydigan tranzaksiyalarni amalga oshirish imkonini beruvchi texnik jihatlarga oydinlik kiritib beriladi.

ANNOTATION

This comprehensive article explores the concepts of the Dark Net and the Deep Net, exploring illegal activities and popular markets on the closed networks of the Internet. An in-depth analysis of the distinguishing features and functions of the Dark and Deep Net, and the technical aspects that enable anonymity, encryption and untraceable transactions in these networks are clarified.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой всеобъемлющей статье рассматриваются концепции Даркнета и Глубокой сети, исследуются незаконные действия и популярные рынки в закрытых сетях Интернета. Углубленный анализ отличительных особенностей и функций темной и глубокой сети, а также технических аспектов, которые обеспечивают анонимность, шифрование и

НЕОТСЛЕЖИВАЕМЫЕ ТРАНЗАКЦИИ В ЭТИХ СЕТЯХ, УТОЧНЯЮТСЯ.

INTRODUCTION

Threats to cyber security have grown in recent years on a global scale. Cybercriminals benefited from misaligned networks during the epidemic as businesses shifted to remote working environments.

The Internet is a special world known to many and where people spend most of their time. The surface of the Internet, and the part that most people see and use every day, is known as the “Surface web” or “Clear net”. More specifically, the surface web is the collection of all open web pages on a server that can be accessed by any known search engine. Although it is only five or ten percent of all the information on the Internet and the possibilities of the Internet, it seems to be enough for ordinary human life. Beneath the surface web lies a limited and obscure part of the internet, which can be divided into two main categories: the “Deep web” and the “Dark web”.

The deep web is a secret network of websites that can only be accessed with a specialized web browser. It is used to maintain the privacy and anonymity of online activity, which is useful for both legitimate and illicit uses [1]. The use of it for extremely criminal activities has also been reported, even though some people use it to avoid government censorship.

The dark web is a secret network of internet sites that can only be accessed with a specialized web browser. It is used to keep online activity secret and confidential, which may be useful in both legal and illicit uses. While some people use it to avoid government restrictions, it has also been used for very unlawful conduct [2].

There is a lot of misunderstanding among these two, and some sources and scholars openly interchange them. However, the Dark Web is not the Deep Web; it is merely a subset of the Deep Web. The Dark Web is based on darknets, or

networks where trustworthy peers interact. TOR, Freenet, and the Invisible Internet Project (I2P) are examples of Dark Web platforms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are several methods that be used for conducting this research, such as literature review, case studies, data analysis, comparative analysis.

The adoption of multi-factor authentication methods, which require more than one verification element for access to sensitive data, is one key solution. Passwords, biometric data, and smart card tokens may be used in conjunction.

Consider the distinctions between the word "public," "private," and "secret" to assist to recall the variances between the surface web, the deep web, and the dark web. The top layer of the web is completely open to the public. The individual or organization who uploaded it is unconcerned about who has access to it or what may be done with it. To take an actual instance, someone probably has no concern who knows their name or the color of their hair in a huge gathering. The deep web, on the contrary, is confidential. The typical individual does not reveal what they're doing with just anyone; they only share it with those who need to know. For instance, you could tell your closest companion about a personal problem, but you would not tell the grocery store clerk. The dark web is private. This is similar to purposefully concealing information from others and not wanting others to learn. This does not have to be deep, dark secrets—for example, not even your closest friends need to know the password to your email account.

RESULTS

Using the mining tunnel figurative language, the Dark Web would be the areas of the Deep Web that require highly specialized tools or equipment to reach. It is further down, giving site owners greater reasons to keep their material secret.

Thus, this definition encompasses dynamic web pages, banned sites (such as those that require a CAPTCHA to access), unlinked sites, private sites (such as

those that require login credentials), non-HTML/contextual/scripted material, and limited-access networks. Limited-access networks cover all resources and services that would not ordinarily be available with a regular network setup, providing intriguing opportunities for bad actors to operate partially or completely unnoticed by law enforcement. Sites with domain names registered on Domain Name System (DNS) roots not managed by the Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN) and, as a result, URLs with nonstandard top-level domains (TLDs) that generally require a specific DNS server to properly resolve [3].

As analyzing the deep web, it is appropriate to consider its differences and specific aspects from the surface network. The deep web: portions of the internet that are not publicly accessible (i.e. private), are not indexed by search engines, and are accountable. Because of authentication requirements or because it is part of an internal network, access is restricted. With the authentication requirements, accountability is in some ways much higher than on the surface web [4].

As a result, when people think of the dark web, they typically associate it with online drug markets, data trades, and other unlawful activities. Despite this, there are plenty of people who use the dark web for very good reasons, including political dissidents and others who want to keep certain information hidden.

Regarding the research and scientific research conducted by Uzbek scientists on this topic, according to S. Gulyamov and I. Rustambekov, the subject of legal regulation of cyber-law is the set of social relations that arise in cyberspace and are regulated by the norms of various legal fields or the sum of which is to be entered and the resulting social relations need to be regulated [5].

The deep web is made up of websites that are only available to logged-in users and web pages that are not connected to other hyperlinks (such as stub web pages that are dynamically generated on demand by site scripts and are not directly linked to). Password-protected users and websites are accessible.

The content of web pages that are not linked from other sites is not indexed since the search bot cannot access such pages. So, a typical user won't be able to access a Deep Web site or web page without knowing its URL [6].

The Deep Web also contains websites whose owners have chosen not to allow their content to be indexed by search engines (for example, using the "robots.txt" file), as well as websites and web pages that have been given permission to prevent unauthorized users from reading their content. In this instance, it is difficult to access or fully read the website's content without knowing the login information and/or password.

Over the past couple of years, a massive amount of Deep Web pages have been scouted, examined, and classified based on the language used. This provided a peek of the likely locations of Deep Web users [7].

English was the primary language of choice for at least 2,154 of the 3,454 successfully scouted domains in terms of raw number of domains. This accounts for around 62% of the total number of sites. This was followed by Russian (228 domains) and French (189 domains, which might include French and Canadian-French sites).

However, accessing the deep web already poses a number of risks. Some users use the power of the deep internet to bypass local restrictions and access TV and movie services that are not available in some areas. In the dark waters of the deep web, it is possible to download pirated copies of music files or movies that have not yet been released in theaters.

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH RESULTS

As many people think the deep vs dark nets are not available only for illicit purposes, but for legal, complex as well as complicated activities, services. There are more than just sites for criminals on them. Some collected several links that may be useful to ordinary law-abiding citizens.

For example, libraries After the Russian-language library "Flibust" was

blocked on the surface Internet, it moved to the "deep". There you can find thousands of books in Russian. Flibusta has its own pages on the deep web and on the I2P dark web. Other notable deep web book resources include Verbal Bogatyr and the Imperial Library of Trantor [8].

Also according to this article, following information can be found in the deep web.

- Rosjustice. Database of public court decisions from all over Russia.
- Image hosting. Anonymous image hosting, where you can upload jpg, png or gif files up to 20 megabytes in size for free.
- Scientific articles A deep "mirror" of the Sci-Hub portal, which allows you to download scientific articles for free.
- Community of fighters with censorship. The multilingual We Fight Censorship community publishes materials that, for one reason or another, have been recognized as banned in different countries.
- Question and answer service. The English-language Hidden Answers service works on the same principle as Mail.ru Answers. Some users ask questions, while others answer them. The main difference from similar “surface” platforms is the subject matter of the questions. They are mainly dedicated to cybersecurity and the deep web. Although there are quite ordinary thematic sections, for example, about relationships or food.
- Search engine. If you want to search for something on the deep web yourself, you can use a system that allows you to search for working sites on the deep web.

The deep web's content consists of search engines, paid sites, private databases, and pages that are not indexed by the dark web. Each search engine uses bots to crawl websites and add new content to the search engine's index. It is unclear how large the deep web is, but most experts believe that search engines

crawl and index less than 1% of all content accessible through the web [9].

Although the deep web's material is not indexed by traditional search engines, it is frequently accessible. Accessing stuff in the deep web is quite secure, and the majority of internet users do so on a regular basis. Accessing data on a deep web site is as simple as logging into Gmail or LinkedIn, or checking in to the Wall Street Journal.

As user accounts on the deep web include a wealth of personal information that thieves may be interested in, access to most of the deep web is prohibited. Users will never have access to the deep web, including the dark web. Spam and phishing attempts may begin on a dark web marketplace, but malware is only released when a victim downloads anything infected from that marketplace. An assault would not be launched from the dark web site.

Dark web marketplaces are online markets where users may purchase and sell illegal items and services while remaining anonymous on the dark web. The products and services on offer vary from stolen credit card information to exploit kits and hired hackers to adverts for hitmen services [10].

Statistics suggest that people have been coordinating unlawful deals through the Internet since the 1970s, according to an analysis of the early Deep Web black marketplaces. These early examples, however, were via restricted networks, and the actual exchange of money and products had to be done in person. With the introduction of cryptocurrencies, it has become not only feasible but also simple to conduct online transactions anonymously without leaving a financial trail. As a result, online illegal products selling has become ubiquitous, and vast dark web markets have emerged [11].

Silk Road was the first of these markets that linked the Darknet to Bitcoin. Ross Ulbricht founded Silk Road in February 2011. Silk Road established the benchmark for darknet markets during the following two years. When it was taken down in October 2013, and Ross Ulbricht was arrested, the site had sold around

\$183 million in goods and services.

Some popular sites which have good feedbacks and more clients are the follows: AlphaBay Market, Asap Market, Incognito Market, MGM Grand Market, Majestic Garden, Nemesis Market, Versus Market, Kingdom Market, Bohemia Market [12].

According to the DarknetStats site, **AlphaBay** is a notorious dark web marketplace established in 2014 that, according to the FBI, was the largest darknet marketplace ever. Authorities took down the platform in 2017 during Operation Bayonet, although they were unable to apprehend several of its employees, including its co-founder and security administrator DeSnake.

AlphaBay is a principle-driven, vision-oriented, and community-focused black market store and forum. It has competent leadership, unsurpassed security, and competent and well-trained staff available 24/7. It is the marketplace that pioneered many of the features that are now commonplace on other sites, such as sticky listings, highlighted listings, autosshops, monero as a payment method, PGP-signed addresses, shared account access for sellers, and so on.

As a second top store **Asean Market** is popular. It was founded as of January and will be live in March 2020. The safety and security of their users is always their first priority [13]. Asean Market was designed from the ground up by skilled developers, hence it is free of defects.

The administrators hope to build an ongoing store with attractive features that will become the Darknet's next leading marketplace.

Renaming of the Asean Market, **ASAP Market** is considered as the most dependable market platform since it is created with top-notch efficiency and safety. We are proud to have been the first to launch DeadDrop and the Maps function. Deaddrop marketplace provides the finest user-friendly and strong safety features.

Third biggest store **Incognito Market** is a hidden web store that earned a

reputation for itself by offering ground-breaking capabilities that had never been seen before on the darknet [14]. Because it rigorously prohibits fraud-related commodities on its site, Incognito store is mostly drugs market. On the market, there is a good assortment of items. Buyers may utilize the secure escrow system to pay for their favorite things in major crypto currencies such as bitcoin and xmr. Thanks to the expert administrators who made this possible, the procedure of registering users through order placement is very straightforward and intuitive. Tor browser may be used to safely visit Incognito Market (javascript must be disabled).

Also in this statistic site gives the list of Scam Markets, like as Aurora Market, Big Blue Market, Dark Fox Market, Dark0de Reborn, Empire Market, Vice City Market, World Market [15].

Unlike in the cybercriminal underground, most Deep Web operations have more visible, if not catastrophic, consequences in the world as it is. Many of the harmful instruments and solutions available on the cybercriminal black market may be utilized to make money. An assassin services, for scenario, clearly serve a distinct, more nefarious function in the Deep Web.

VAWTRAK virus is a type of financial services Trojan that spreads through emails that are phishing. Each of the samples connects with a set of command and control (C&C) servers, the IP addresses of which are obtained by downloading an encrypted icon file (favicon.ico) from several hard-coded TOR sites. This has the benefit of anonymizing the location of a criminal server but not the users who use it, which is not a problem because all of the "users" are infected computers [16]. There are other dark web-only email providers, the most well-known of which being Torbox and Mail2Tor, which can only be accessed using a Tor browser.

Despite its nefarious reputation, the dark web serves many lawful and legal functions. The dark web is frequently associated with scary and menacing images. While the dark web may include some dubious information, it also has a number

of beneficial applications, such as assisting individuals in circumventing government censorship and offering an extra layer of anonymity to email services. We'll look at Legally Benefits for the Dark Web:

Avoid Political Censorship. While anonymity on the web has allowed unlawful content to flourish on the dark web, it has also made it possible for residents in authoritarian nations to circumvent internet restrictions imposed by their government.

The services for Anonymous Email. While there are a number of secured email services accessible via the surface web, customers seeking more privacy can visit the dark web. ProtonMail, which is backed by the Tor network and preserves user privacy, combats censorship, and avoids user monitoring, is the most well-known email service on the dark web.

Journalists Collaborate Anonymously. Some people, such as whistleblowers, may feel more comfortable contacting media anonymously. SecureDrop is a communication app that leverages the Tor network to allow sources and journalists to communicate anonymously. It is extensively utilized by news organizations such as Forbes, Vice Media, and the New Yorker.

Visit News Sources. While the internet is available to anybody with an internet connection globally, foreign governments occasionally block news websites. The dark web has shown to be an effective weapon in combating this type of censorship, with the investigative journalism company ProPublica establishing a presence there in 2016. Citizens all across the globe may visit ProPublica's Tor-accessible website anonymously, even if their government has prohibited it on the surface web. The New York Times and the BBC have also followed in ProPublica's footsteps and built dark web versions of their websites on the Tor network.

Make an anonymous call to the CIA. The CIA established an official presence on the dark web in 2019. Although the dark web may appear to be an

unexpected location for a government organization to be present, the website is intended for those who want to connect with the CIA but are worried about being monitored.

Academic Research Access. Academic research might be difficult to obtain. One may have to pay a large sum just to read a single article. On the dark web, the American Journal of Freestanding Research Psychology attempted to tackle this dilemma by hosting academic publications for free. Even better, you don't have to worry about the legality of obtaining the papers because every academic article featured on the site was submitted by the original writers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there are several reasons why a "hidden" Internet is needed. There can be many reasons for creating pages on the deep web or one of the dark webs. The main advantage of closed networks over shallow networks is, of course, anonymity. Therefore, the hidden Internet is often used for illegal activities.

Darknet markets sell drugs, weapons, fake documents, and even people. It is also possible to find contract killer contacts on the darknet. In addition, user data often gets into the dark Internet - hackers who have access to the database periodically transfer it to closed networks. Local markets are the easiest to pay with cryptocurrency - again, because it allows you to remain anonymous.

Another option for illegal activity on the dark web is the distribution of pirated content. However, it is very active even "on the surface". In countries where the authorities actively deal with piracy, the dark web helps free content lovers. The deep web and dark web have gained popularity due to their frequent use by criminals. However, illegal activity is not the only use of hidden networks. There, for example, human rights defenders and journalists of totalitarian and authoritarian countries create their pages. On the dark web, they fear neither censorship nor authority. The deep web is a great platform to fight for freedom of

speech, and it can be used for more than just illegal purposes.

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